

Title: Efficient internal and external trade with Blockchain and Bitcoin technology, the ISBIT Exchange case

Name: Sebastian Acosta Checa

Affiliation: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Actuary & Maths

INTRODUCTION:

Blockchain, the technology that governs the creation and exchange of digital assets, is a public book, a collective transaction memory that allows you to track transactions and make payments without having to rely on an intermediary, to which all participants in the system have access. In addition to Blockchain, another necessary "ingredient" is the "Consensus Mechanism" that establishes the protocols or rules by which the participants coincide periodically and by which the sequence of transactions that have occurred with cryptographic certainty is impossible to rape.

In the case of bitcoin, the most famous blockchain of all, it is through the consensus mechanism that the "coins" or units of account can not be spent more than once and the rules governing monetary policy are exercised and the introduction of new currencies in circulation.

In the coming years, perhaps, we will see versions of Digital Assets created by governments, corporations, commercial banks, international institutions such as the IMF or World Bank and others.

AIM:

To develop an efficient, profitable, and less cost-effective industry for monetary, commercial, foreign trade and remittance transactions, for the benefit of the Mexican economy and society. It follows that it is part of our objectives to efficiently operate companies by reducing the cost, duration and risk of their transactions as well as optimize the use of human resources by automating treasury management tasks and other areas that require payments or currency exchange.

It is also part of our goals to help corporations evolve and become Intelligent Enterprises, with processes that are operated by software freeing the time of workers for more creative tasks.

In addition, we seek to support companies that specialize in sending money to improve their social objectives, since the benefits indirectly impact migrants in the form of lower costs and quicker availability of the money they send to their families.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Since ISBIT EXCHANGE is already operating with 1,140 members, we decided to apply the algorithms previously described in the systems in production (<https://isbit.co>) to obtain empirical information that allows us to estimate the value at risk. We find that 99% of the time the proportion of Total Liabilities found in the Hotwallet is between $\min(V_t) = 2.65\%$ and $\max(V_t) = 6.45\%$ and has an expected value of $E(V_t) = 5.87\%$.

Control Algorithm 2 is simpler than the previous one. As parameters (or rather constants) of operation of the algorithm we have 3 preset values. First, $v_{targetj}$ the percentage of the liabilities of the currency j that is our "goal" or goal to have in the corresponding Hotwallet. Second, we establish, v_{minj} , the minimum tolerance percentage for the level of funds in the Hotwallet corresponding to currency j . Third, we establish, v_{maxj} , the maximum percentage tolerance threshold for the level of funds.

RESULTS:

1140 USERS, faster, safer and cheaper national and international payments without banking intermediation

CONCLUSIONS:

What ISBIT proposes is a paradigm shift. We seek to democratize international payments and replace the foreign oligopoly that has controlled international payments for decades.

Let us see the offer of companies that together offer a substitute / alternative service to ISBIT.

In the process of international payments where it is necessary to convert currency, CLS BANK services are generally used. In Mexico, companies do not have direct access to the CLS platform, only some large financial institutions. ISBIT unlike CLS gives market access to all those who have legitimate reasons to exchange currencies electronically.

Also in the process of international payments SWIFT is commonly used as the infrastructure to send encrypted messages, send instructions and notify the parties involved of the status of payments. SWIFT's high degree of centralization has caused this infrastructure to be hacked repeatedly. We carry out the tasks of tracking fund transfers, notarization and transmission of messages guaranteed through block chains that have never been violated. Performing messaging, clearing and currency conversion with a single provider eliminates complexity.

Some banks in Mexico offer the international transfer service. Examples are CITI or HSBC. A limitation of the services offered by these institutions is the lack of an application programming interface (API) that allows the automation of the processes of sending international payments as well as their tracking. When payments are controlled from the organization's software (Business Management Systems or ERPs such as SAP, ORACLE, IBM, etc.), human error is eliminated and transactions can be made faster. Also the exchange rate offered by these suppliers is usually expensive as they apply a "margin of error" to take into account the movement in the price of the currencies involved in the transaction during the period of time it takes to complete the process.

KEYWORDS:

Blockchain, Payments, Banks, Money, Exchange, Digital Assets

BIOGRAPHY:

Sebastian Acosta Checa, Sebastian's fields of interest are the intersection of cryptography, artificial intelligence and finance. He studied Mathematics and Acted in the Faculty of Sciences of the UNAM and has extensive experience in the Financial Services and Technology sector. Sebastian previously worked on the development of a mobile payment application for ING BANK. Sebastian developed an Intelligent Financial Information Analysis tool for PricewaterhouseCoopers. In the area of Risk Management, Sebastian participated in SM4RT in the development of a tool based on Neural Networks to detect fraud in credit card transactions.

Notes:

www.isbit.co

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